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Recruiting international talent:

The importance of language skills for career perspectives of foreign engineering students in Germany

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ABSTRACT

Facing a global competition for highly qualified workers in the STEM fields, German employers are realizing the great potential of degree-seeking international students of technical disciplines. In contrast to foreign talent which needs to be recruited from abroad, a most valuable asset is seen in the cultural and language skills those students have supposedly already acquired during their studies in Germany.

At the Ruhr-Universität Bochum, the Project ELLI2 aims at improving the conditions of teaching and learning in engineering education. The cooperative project of three German universities is funded within the Teaching Quality Pact by the German Federal Government and States. In its key area *Globalization*, the project focuses on aspects of internationalization in higher education contexts.

This paper will present selected findings of a recently completed dissertation in the field of Social Sciences which deals with academic migration in engineering education and was conducted in association with the project work of ELLI2. It will highlight results of a mixed-method approach that investigated motivations of international engineering students who come to Germany for their master's studies. One of its key findings is that - despite their great willingness to learn German before and during their academic migration – international students struggle with the language requirements of the German labour market. Conclusions will be drawn with regard to the importance that both international students and German employers place on cultural capital in the form of language skills when it comes to career perspectives at the interface between university and labour market.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a global competition for talent, highly qualified immigration is increasingly regarded by the representatives of German politics and economy as one of multiple measures to prevent a shortage of talent, especially in the fields of science and technology. International students who have already studied in Germany are regarded as especially valuable: Ideally, they have already gained experiences in German culture, possibly even work experience, and acquired German language skills during their studies. Furthermore, they are available for the German labour market directly after graduating [1]; [2].

For their higher education report 2015, the Association for the Promotion of German Science and Humanities together with McKinsey conducted a survey with 230 German companies, asking them among other things about their view on foreign students as potential professionals [3]. The survey results indicated that German companies increasingly rely on foreign graduates of German universities in order to meet their demand for qualified personnel: Half of the companies are already relying on foreign graduates today and 66% are convinced that the situation will tighten in the future [ibid.]. 65% of the companies wish for a recruitment strategy of international students which is in line with the demands of the German labour market and they want political strategies and higher education institutions to improve the transition from university into job market [ibid., p. 20].

During the last two decades, the influence of globalization on the German higher education system has led to a wide-spread implementation of international study programmes, particularly on the master's level. Today, there are more than 1,100 internationally oriented master degree programmes and 160 international Bachelor programmes offered by German universities [4]. In order to make up for their shrinking student numbers by the end of the 20th century, the technical disciplines and engineering subjects were among the first to implement international (English-taught) programmes [5]. Such international study programmes attract talent from all over the world and thus have a great potential for winning international graduates who stay on to work in Germany.

At the Ruhr-Universität Bochum (RUB), research was conducted on three international master's programmes in the engineering departments. The project ELLI2 in its key area Globalization focuses on internationalization in engineering education, fostering incoming and outgoing student mobility. In cooperation with the project's work, a doctoral research study in social sciences was conducted on academic migration in engineering education [6]. The main research aims were to find out about motivations of international students who come to Germany for their studies and about their potential willingness to stay on for the job market after graduation. The following chapters will present selected results on the importance of language skills that serve as cultural capital for international engineering students who come to Germany.

2 LANGUAGE AS CULTURAL CAPITAL FOR INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

2.1 Research object

The engineering faculties of the Ruhr-Universität Bochum (RUB) offer three international master's programmes: Laser and Photonics, Computational Engineering and Materials Science and Simulations. All three master degree courses are taught entirely in English and international applicants do not have to have any German language skills in order to apply. While they are open for applications from international students as well as for Germans, there are only very few German students in these programmes. Most students are from (East) Asia and among the most common countries of origin are India, Pakistan, Syria, China and Iran.

The research conducted within the framework of a dissertation project in the social sciences [6] aimed at investigating the motivations of international students who come to Germany as degree-seeking students. The focus was on understanding their reasons for choosing the international master's programmes and whether they plan to turn their academic migration into labour migration by deciding to stay on to work in Germany after graduating.

2.2 Theoretical background and central hypothesis

The theoretical background of the investigation was based on the sociological capital theories by Bourdieu: In his capital theory, the late French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu differentiates between three forms of capital, namely economic, social and cultural capital (the latter being sub-divided further). He puts these three capital forms on a level with forms of power, each having their own way of institutionalization and making appearances in societal exchange depending on their respective application and transformation.

Economic capital for Bourdieu is the capital form that can be most directly converted, in its monetary form. Social capital comprises all social, societal and familiar relations and contacts, which can occur in a more or less institutionalized form and which rely on social acts of exchange in order to be converted [7]. Cultural capital, according to Bourdieu, exists in three different forms: 1. As incorporated cultural capital which is permanently acquired and internalized by its owner, 2. As objectified cultural which exists in cultural goods as material form (such as books or paintings) and 3., as institutionalized cultural capital, which is an objectified version of incorporated cultural capital, e.g. in the form of educational certificates and titles (ibid., p.187).

With regard to the international students of the three master's programmes, one key hypothesis was that German language skills serve as incorporated cultural capital on which the students place a certain value for their academic migration and which they try to accumulate during their studies in Germany, so that it can be transferred into job opportunities on the German labour market.

2.3 Methodological approach and research design

To examine this hypothesis (along with further hypotheses regarding also economic and social capital) from the students' viewpoint, an investigation was conducted in 2015 and 2016 with a mixed-method approach of quantitative and qualitative research methods: The first stage of the investigation consisted of a quantitative online-survey that was sent to all international students enrolled in the three engineering master's degree courses at that time (N=266). With a final participation number of 84 (after three reminders), the response rate was almost 32%. The second stage of the research design was a follow-up study with a total of 17 semi-structured, qualitative interviews. The interview guidelines were designed in a way that the results of the quantitative stage would either be confirmed or disproved [6].

3 RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1 German language skills before migration

While “having English as a teaching” language was among the top 3 reasons for choosing their study programme in Germany, more than half of the international students started to learn German while they were still in their home countries. 53% of the survey participants had German skills before their academic migration and 36% had taken German classes in their home country. The largest group of those with German skills before migration were on a beginners' level, while 20% each reached a lower intermediate or intermediate language level and 7% an upper intermediate level. The fact that so many students had learned German before migrating although German skills are not a prerequisite of their international master's programmes indicates that they consciously prepared themselves for Germany as a host country and that they regarded German skills as very important. All students (those who had German skills before migration as well as those who didn't) furthermore state that they expected to improve their German language skills during their studies in Germany.

Fig. 1. German language skills before the academic migration to Germany [6]

3.2 Learning German while studying in Germany

The majority (88%) of all participants (N=82) state that they are currently learning German while they are studying in Germany. Only 12% do not actively pursue an improvement of their German language skills. Asked for the way that they learn German (multiple answers being possible), the largest group of students with 38% named classical German language classes. Further common ways of learning named by the participants were interaction with German-speaking people in the context of their studies (14%) as well as outside university (17%) and autodidactic language learning (16%). Online language courses (8%) or language tandems (4%) were named less often. Further forms of language learning that were described by participants in an open text field included self-learning with German movies and books, scientific literature as well as a project called “Sprachstunde”. This project is a student initiative started by the student council of the master’s programme “Computational Engineering” designed to foster language interaction between German and international students: German students (usually of philological disciplines) meet about once per week with a group of international engineering students (in a relation of about 1:5) in order to talk German. Participation is generally on a voluntary basis, but the study coordinators of Computational Engineering award Credit Points for regular attendance that can be recognized as part of the curriculum.

While most students learn German, their satisfaction with the progress they are making in learning the language is rather moderate: on a scale from 1 to 7 (1 representing “very satisfied” and 7 representing “not satisfied at all”), the mean value of all answers lies at 3.9, the median at 4.

3.3 Language skills and the search for part-time jobs

The quantitative results furthermore revealed an interesting connection between language skills and the search for a (part-time) job or internship. More than half of the international students who are searching for work during their studies described the job search as very difficult (33%) or difficult (30%). In an open answer question, participants were asked to describe the reasons for their difficulties in finding work. For a quantitative analysis, all free-text answers were coded and assigned to four different categories: All answers related to a lack of German language skills were coded as “German”, answers related to a lack of information for the job search as “Information”. If there were no specific difficulties perceived in the job search, answers were assigned to the category “None” and the category “Other” was chosen for different reasons which were named only once each. The majority (66%) of all participants in this section (N=38), described problems of the category “German”. Only 8% had difficulties related to lack of information and 18% described other difficulties.

Fig. 2. Reasons for difficulties in finding a job/internship during studies [6]

Evidently, insufficient German skills are perceived as one of the main obstacles in finding a job during their studies. Language skills also play a role when it comes to choosing potential employers: Answering the question which type of career they would like to pursue after graduating from their master’s, 46% of the international students stated that they would like to work as a research assistant or PhD candidate. About 40% would like to work in the private sector, while 12% are not sure yet and 2% select “other” fields of employment. The largest group of those who plan to work in the private sector (65%, N=40) would like to work in a large company with more than 250 employees. 32.5% would like to work in a medium-sized company with up to 250 employees and only one person wants to work in a small company with up to 50 employees. This is probably due to the fact that larger companies generally tend to be more international and accept English as working language.

3.4 Interview results

During the interviews, it was confirmed that learning German is very important for the international students. Most of them try to improve their German language skills during their studies but are not satisfied with the progress they are making. Several interview partners also stated that they had underestimated the importance of German for finding a job:

“My impression from the internet was like – it would be much easier to find a job after your studies. But the point that I pretty much underestimated was the German language. In that time, I didn’t think that German language will play such a big role in my career here.”

“Before coming I thought, it’s not that hard...it’s easier to find rather than what I see now. Actually they need a high level of their language and I didn’t know that and the choices, I thought there would be more...I mean it’s a little bit competitive now and it’s harder to find a job from what I thought before.”

With regard to her career interests and the respective offer of subjects in Germany, one student even ponders whether it might have been better to choose a German-speaking master's course:

“Thinking about it now, I think I would have preferred to take German classes before and then probably would have done a course in German, just because as I said, I am interested in automotive industries, and a lot of these courses are done in German and a lot of these options are in German. So I think, if I had options to do it again, I would probably come for 6 months or so taking German classes and then maybe do a German degree program. But when I was applying at that time, I didn't really have an option to do a German program...even to consider that. The program being in English was definitely one of my deciding factors.”

Apparently, the high relevance of fluent German skills for the labour market of the host country comes as a surprise to many and causes preoccupations with the international students. However, the interviews revealed a difference in the perceived importance of language skills for careers in industry vs. science. Many interview participants who plan to apply as doctoral candidates are convinced that English is the predominant language of research work:

“[I]n Germany, if you want to find an internship or job you must speak at least good German. But in [our research institute], we are oriented on research and we have to do publications in English. My focus is research so actually I don't need to learn German.”

Another student describes learning German as a sort of plan B in case his plans for a career in research should fail: “[I]f I complete my master's and do not get a PhD position after a period of time, then I would also prefer to learn German. That's my plan, after my master's to get some good knowledge about German”.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The research results presented in this paper have shown that for international engineering students who come to Germany in order to obtain a degree, German language skills are very important. Although the international master degree courses at RUB are taught completely in English and German is no prerequisite, more than half of the students already learned German while they were still in their home countries. During their studies in Germany, the majority of students try to improve their German skills. This indicates that they regard German language skills as incorporated cultural capital which they try to accumulate.

Confronted with the requirements of the German job market, however, the international students encounter difficulties due to insufficient German skills and many seem to realize that they have underestimated the importance of fluency in the host country's language before coming here. With regard to potential working fields, many turn either to scientific careers or want to work in medium or large companies where it is more probably that fluency in German is not required.

In order to make the transition from university to labour market more easy for students in international study programmes, projects such as the student initiative „Sprachstunde“ might be a good option. Only few students are so far learning in language tandems and measures which bring together international and German students might be beneficial also for regular students in German study courses.

From the perspective of potential German employers, however, it might be advisable to prepare for the fact that international students are not usually fluent in German after only a few years in Germany, even though they graduated from a German university. At the interface of university and labour market, universities and employers should work together to provide intensive language classes at the career start of international talents.

REFERENCES

- [1] DAAD, Prognos (2013), Studentische Mobilität u. ihre finanziellen Effekte auf das Gastland. Available onlien: <https://eu.daad.de/medien/eu.daad.de.2016/dokumente/service/medien-und-publikationen/studien-und-auswertungen/>
- [2] OECD (2013), Zuwanderung ausländischer Arbeitskräfte. Paris: OECD.
- [3] Stifterverband für die Deutsche Wissenschaft; McKinsey (2015): Hochschulbildungsreport 2020. Jahresbericht 2015: Internationale Bildung, p. 18.
- [4] German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) (2019). Online database of international study programmes in Germany, available online: <https://www.daad.de/deutschland/studienangebote/international-programs/en/>
- [5] Maiworm, Friedhelm (Ed.) (2002), English-language-taught degree programmes in European higher education. Trends and success factors. Bonn: Lemmens (ACA Papers on international cooperation in education)
- [6] Strenger, Natascha (2018), Akademische Migration und internationale Masterstudiengänge in den Ingenieurwissenschaften. Dissertation. Bochum: Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Universitätsbibliothek
- [7] Bourdieu, Pierre (1983), Ökonomisches Kapital, kulturelles Kapital, soziales Kapital. In: Kreckel, R. (Hg.): Soziale Ungleichheiten. Soziale Welt. Sonderband 2. Göttingen, p. 183–198